

Replicability across populations (S7.2)

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1 Bos taurus

1.1 Iran

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

1.2 Uganda

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

2 Capra

2.1 Australia

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

2.2 France

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

2.3 Iran (C. aegagrus)

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

2.4 Iran

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

2.5 Italy

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

2.6 Morocco

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

3 Chlorocebus sabaues

3.1 Barbados

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

3.2 Central Afr. Rep.

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

3.3 Ethiopia

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

3.4 Gambia

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

3.5 Kenya

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

3.6 Nevis

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

3.7 Saint Kitts

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

3.8 South Africa

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

3.9 Zambia

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

4 Equus caballus

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

5 Homo sapiens

5.1 African

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

5.2 Admixed American

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

5.3 East Asian

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

5.4 European

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

5.5 South Asian

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

6 Ovis

6.1 Iran

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

6.2 Iran (*O. orientalis*)

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

6.3 Iran (*O. vignei*)

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

6.4 Various

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

6.5 Morocco

A: Expected DFE for mutations

B: Expected DFE for substitutions

C: Observed DFE for substitutions

D: Observed DFE for polymorphisms

E: Site frequency spectrum

F: S as function of S_0 for each class

